

Understanding Conjunction in Vedic Astrology

15 Comments / Blog / By Deepanshu Giri

The conjunction of two energies in the sky will result in an energy that will govern the life of the native, In All the books in Jyotish we read there are effects of conjunction written and these are called yog.

My objective in this article will be to give you an understanding of the energies so you can decipher the output yourself based on your own understanding, As one combination can have multiple outcomes but for every chart to specify the result you need to understand the nature of energy first.

The division of planets is done into two parts- Active and Passive.

Passive Energy- This means whatever your actions will be the result will be in some other form in some other area after a period of time as passive energy give output in some other form.

Such as You are working hard today and doing everything good according to your understanding, but you are not getting desired results which you were expecting, What humans fail to understand is that the result of this karma will be delivered somewhere in future in a much more appreciated form.

Let us suppose you read a book and even memorize a few chapters of this and you are perfectly capable of answering a few questions from this book as well- This is active energy- While over a period of time, the knowledge in this book helps us understand the bigger picture and you truly understand the meaning behind the words this is passive energy from Mercury to Jupiter.

Active energy planets are—Mars, Mercury, Venus

Passive Energy planets—Saturn, Jupiter

Sun/Moon- Continuous source of energy combustion while Rahu and Ketu are continuous sources of consumption, In terms of electrical engineering Source and Sink.

Active energy- When you do an action, and you get instant results such as you study and you can memorize the chapter, you go to the gym and you can see visible changes in your body, when active and passive energy planets intermix the result is somewhat depending on the energy of signs than such as Jupiter & Mercury, Mars & Saturn.

Let us discuss an example of the conjunction of Saturn and Mars.

Saturn-Mars Conjunction—When Mars is in the grip of Saturn and highly afflicted the energy of native is completely drained as Mars is the active energy of the Universe while Saturn is the passive energy, We are talking about the scenario where Saturn is more powerful than Rahu such as Saturn/Rahu/Mars in Capricorn or Saturn/Mars in Libra where Saturn is exalted.

This means the active energy of Mars which relates to taking care of physical body needs, taking initiative in life, maintaining a healthy ego and standing up for your own self will be missing as native is now hiding under the shield of passive energy, It is true as well that in this case Saturn will become the shield of this native.

If anyone who will do badly with this native will bring the wrath of Saturn over a period of time as passive energy troubles you by draining you slowly, creating a depletion in your energy bit by bit, you are ignorant towards this energy drain until and unless it becomes a source of misery for you.

One of the remedies of Saturn Mars will be to increase the active energy of Mars which will be taking care of physical health, Every day spending some time with friends, Being aware if someone steps on toes and being ready for worse to fight.

A person with bad Mars is afraid of fighting and wants to maintain peace at any cost, but this is how you balance the active and Passive energies in the chart and see the result as well.

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